

Molecular Adducts of Triphenyltin Pseudohalides with Schiff Bases*

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Triphenyltin pseudohalides form molecular adducts of the formulae $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnX}\cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnX}\cdot \text{L}'$ ($\text{X}=\text{NCS}, \text{NCO}, \text{N}_3$) with different types of Schiff bases. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance and ir spectral data. A positive shift of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ upon adduct formation indicates coordination from the azomethine N atom of the bases.

SEVERAL reports have appeared during the last decade on the Schiff base complexes of organotin(IV) halides containing the ligands in their neutral or deprotonated forms^{1,2}. Since the organotin(IV) pseudohalides are known to form stable adducts with a number of N and O donors³⁻⁶, it was considered worthwhile to examine their Lewis acidity towards Schiff bases. This paper reports the synthesis and characterization of several hitherto unknown adducts of Ph_3SnX ($\text{X}=\text{NCS}, \text{NCO}$ or N_3) with the following bases.

$\text{R}=\text{H}$, $\text{R}'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (L_2), $p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ (L_3), NH_2 (L_4), $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ (L_5); $\text{R}=\text{5,6-benzo}$, $\text{R}'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (L_6), $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ (L_7).

It is observed that $\text{N,N}'\text{-bis(salicylaldehyde)}$ ethylenediamine (L_1) forms molecular adducts of 1 : 1 stoichiometry, while other bases yield products with 1 : 2 (Lewis acid : Schiff base) mole ratio, irrespective of the nature of pseudohalide group.

Experimental

Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with aniline, p -toluidine, hydrazine, 2-ethanolamine or ethylenediamine. Triphenyltin pseudohalides were prepared by the methods reported elsewhere⁶⁻⁸. The adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis acids with the bases in appropriate molar ratios using benzene or methanol/acetonitrile mixture as the reaction medium.

In a representative experiment, a solution of Ph_3SnNCS (1.2 g ; 3 m mole) in benzene (20-25 ml) was added dropwise to a refluxing solution of $\text{N,N}'\text{-bis(salicylaldehyde)}$ ethylenediamine (1.18 g ; 6 m mole) in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for 3-4 hr and on completion of the reaction excess solvent was distilled off. The resulting concentrate on cooling in a deep freeze yielded a crystalline product which was filtered and washed with cold benzene, yield 73%. In some cases the products were isolated from the concentrate by precipitation with pet. ether (60-80°).

Tin content in the molecular adducts was determined gravimetrically as SnO_2 . Analysis for N was carried out at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, on a semimicro scale. Molar conductance of $10^{-3} M$ solution of a few complexes soluble in methanol was measured at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ on a Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. The ir spectra were recorded on a PE 377 spectrophotometer. The analytical data and relevant ir frequencies are summarised in Table I.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are yellow to orange and are thermally stable solids. The elemental analyses correspond to 1 : 2 stoichiometry for all the adducts of triphenyltin pseudohalide with the Schiff bases used, excepting those of $\text{N,N}'\text{-bis(salicylaldehyde)}$ -ethylenediamine which have 1 : 1 composition. The low values of molar conductance ($0.9\text{-}2.6 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of the complexes in methanol indicate the absence of ionic species in solution.

IR spectra: The broad weak band at $\sim 2900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the ligands attributed to stretching vibrations of the intramolecularly H-bonded OH (phenolic) group is shifted to $\sim 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the adducts indicating retention of H-bonded ring in the distorted form⁹. The

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND RELEVANT IR FREQUENCIES FOR TRIPHENYL TIN PSEUDOHALIDE ADDUCTS WITH SCHIFF BASES

Compound	m.p.(b.p.) °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		IR absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)		
		Sn	N	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{as}NCO/N_s$	ν_sNCO/N_s
Ph₃SnX.L						
L₁ X						
L ₁	NCS	67	17.44 (17.56)	6.00 (6.21)	1680 (1619)*	2040 830
L ₁	NCO	92	18.78 (18.65)	6.47 (6.60)	1628	2215 1365
L ₁	N ₃	200d	17.99 (18.03)	10.53 (10.60)	1685	2080 1320
Ph₃SnX.2L						
L₂ NCS						
L ₂	NCS	133	14.48 (14.80)	5.20 (5.23)	1625 (1613)	2040 825
L ₂	NCO	89	15.02 (15.10)	5.20 (5.34)	1628	2210 1370
L ₂	N ₃	251d	15.08 (15.13)	8.79 (8.90)	1622	2090 1330
L ₂	NCS	142	14.20 (14.30)	5.12 (5.06)	1625 (1616)	2040 830
L ₂	N ₃	265d	14.59 (14.61)	8.32 (8.59)	1630	2080 1330
L ₂	NCS	150	17.55 (17.57)	10.20 (10.29)	1610 (1600)	2040 —
L ₂	NCO	114	17.65 (17.87)	10.52 (10.56)	1612	2210 1360
L ₂	N ₃	265d	17.78 (17.92)	14.57 (14.75)	1622	2090 1330
L ₂	NCS	(168/14 mm)	15.98 (16.08)	5.60 (5.69)	1640 (1630)	2025 830
L ₂	N ₃	155d	16.30 (16.48)	9.90 (9.83)	1647	2055 1335
L ₂	NCS	135	13.00 (13.16)	4.60 (4.65)	1630 (1624)	2040 830
L ₂	NCO	108	13.35 (13.40)	4.70 (4.74)	1630	2200 1340
L ₂	N ₃	217d	13.45 (13.39)	7.95 (7.89)	1627	2085 1340
L ₂	NCS	71	14.32 (14.17)	4.92 (5.01)	1638 (1632)	2040 830
L ₂	N ₃	210d	14.45 (14.47)	8.45 (8.51)	1640	2070 1330

* Ligand frequencies in parentheses.

absorption due to ν_{OH} (alcoholic), identified in the spectra of the Schiff bases L₅ at 3330 cm⁻¹ and L₇ at 3360 cm⁻¹, is little affected on adduct formation. Also, a strong band at 1275 ± 15 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the Schiff bases, associated with $\nu(\text{Ph}-\text{O})$ remains almost unaltered on adduct formation. These observations suggest that hydroxy groups of the bases are not involved in complexation¹⁰.

The strong band at 1617 ± 17 cm⁻¹ observed in the spectra of the free Schiff bases due to $\nu_{C=N}$ is shifted to higher wave number upon complexation, indicating coordination from the N atom of the ligands¹⁰⁻¹⁴. However, this positive shift in the $\nu_{C=N}$ frequency is small in case of the adducts with the bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, which may account for the reduced donor ability of these bases¹². In the spectra of the adducts of L₄, the absence of a change in the position of stretching and bending modes of vibrations of the NH₂ group and an increase in the $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{N-N} absorption frequencies by ~ 15 and ~ 40

cm⁻¹, respectively suggest that the azomethine N atom alone is involved in coordination, while the terminal NH₂ group remains free^{15,16}. It is inferred that donor ability of the azomethine group, due to the proximity of the OH group, is greater than the terminal NH₂ group.

The spectra of all the adducts of Ph₃SnNCS consist of strong bands at 2040, 830 and 460 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to $\nu_{as}NCS$, ν_sNCS and δNCS , indicating the presence of N-bonded thiocyanato group¹⁷. The *iso* structure of the cyanate group in the adducts of Ph₃SnNCO is evident from the appearance of strong absorptions at 2200, 1300 and 610 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{as}NCO$, ν_sNCO and δNCO , respectively^{18,19}. The spectra of the adducts of Ph₃SnN₃ also exhibit three characteristic frequencies at 2050, 1330 and 655 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to $\nu_{as}N_3$, ν_sN_3 and δN_3 vibrations, respectively^{8,20}.

The physicochemical data suggest the possibility of an octahedral geometry around the hexacoordinated tin atom.

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